

Comparative Study of Wound Healing in Patients with Diabetes versus Non-Diabetic Patients' Post-Surgery

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Abstract:

Background: Diabetes mellitus severely impairs tissue repair mechanisms and wound healing. Understanding the differences in outcomes between diabetic and non-diabetic surgical patients is essential to clinical management.

Method: This retrospective cohort study includes 100 at Territory care Hospital surgery patients from July 2023 to May 2024. Using medical records, patients were separated into two groups: diabetics (n=50) and non-diabetics (n=50). The two groups were compared using independent samples t-tests and chi-square tests, with a p-value of < 0.05, for wound closure times, infection rates, and further interventions.

Results: Patients with diabetes had a wound closure time of 28 ± 5 days, compared to 21 ± 3 days for non-diabetics (p-value < 0.001). Patients with diabetes had 30% higher wound infections than those without diabetes (12%, p = 0.023). Diabetes patients required more interventions after surgery (40% vs. 18%, p = 0.011).

Conclusion: This study found that diabetics and non-diabetics heal surgical wounds differently. The results show that diabetes-related variables including impaired vascular perfusion and altered immune function delay wound closure and increase infection risk in diabetic surgical patients. Individualised protocols and proactive treatment are needed to help at-risk patients avoid issues and receive the greatest wound care results.

Keywords: Diabetes Mellitus, Surgical Procedures, Wound Healing, Wound Infections, Wound Management.

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Introduction

Patients' recovery after surgery depends on the complex physiological process of wound healing, which affects healthcare costs and outcomes [1]. Wound healing problems can cause hospital stays, morbidity, and infections. Understanding wound healing factors, especially in high-risk patients like diabetics, is essential for clinical management and patient care [2].

Surgical wound healing involves complex biological processes as inflammation, cell proliferation, and tissue remodelling. These methods affect surgery patients' functional and aesthetic outcomes. When wound dehiscence, infection, and poor healing stress patients, recovery periods, healthcare costs, and satisfaction might suffer [3]. Patient-specific wound healing parameters are needed to improve surgical results and lower healthcare costs. Effective wound healing is crucial for surgical success and it impacts recovery time, problems, and patient health.

Healthcare practitioners aim for speedy and complete wound closure to reduce patient discomfort, costs, and recovery time [4]. Diabetes, a chronic metabolic disorder marked by hyperglycemia, can cause systemic complications, including skin problems.

Diabetes slows wound healing due to inadequate microcirculation, collagen formation, and immune function [5]. Chronic hyperglycemia also causes oxidative stress and inflammation, which slow healing. Diabetic wounds are more prone to have issues, heal slowly, and get infections.

Objectives

- To compare surgical patients with and without diabetes for wound-healing rates and quality.
- To determine the frequency of wound-related postoperative complications in both patient groups.

- To identify diabetic features that worsens wound healing.

Wound Healing in Diabetic and Non-Diabetic Patients: [6] study shows that diabetics and non-diabetics heal wounds differently; diabetic wounds

heal and develop complications slower than non-diabetic wounds. In a retrospective study by [7], diabetic surgery patients had a higher incidence of wound infections and longer hospital stays than those without diabetes.

Non-diabetic	Day 1	Day 6	Day 9	Day 9 (positive control)
Diabetic	Day 1	Day 6	Day 9	Day 13 (positive control)

Figure 1: wound healing of the patients (source:[6])

Day \ Group	7	14
Non Diabetic control		
Diabetic control		
PLA Nano fiber		

Figure 2: Wound healing groups and PLA Nano fiber (source:[8])

Factors Affecting Wound Healing in Diabetes:

Multiple factors impair diabetic wound healing. Chronic hyperglycemia partially causes microvascular issues and reduced tissue oxygen delivery [8].

Diabetic neuropathy impairs autonomic and sensory processes, which impede wound sensation and vascular tone, which are essential for healing. Diabetes immunological dysfunction impairs neutrophil activity and cytokine profiles, complicating wound healing during inflammation.

Mechanisms of Impaired Wound Healing in Diabetes:

Diabetes compromises wound healing due to a complex interaction of variables. Hyperglycemia-induced oxidative stress causes endothelial dysfunction and reduced angiogenesis, which hinders wound healing [9]. Elevated hyperglycemia disrupts extracellular matrix production and remodelling, impairing healing tissue structure.

Chronic inflammation delays the proliferative phase of wound healing in diabetic wounds, which slows wound closure.

Current Treatment Strategies for Diabetic Wounds:

Diabetic wounds require interdisciplinary treatment to address pathophysiological reasons. To prevent hyperglycemia complications, strict glycaemic management is standard [10]. Growth factor therapies, negative pressure wound therapy, moist wound dressings, and other advanced wound care methods that stimulate granulation tissue development speed wound closure, according to [11]. Complex diabetic ulcers that have not responded to standard therapy may require skin grafting and debridement. Diabetic wounds' poor healing and susceptibility to complications make treatment difficult. Understanding intricate wound healing mechanisms and developing appropriate treatments will improve diabetes surgery results.

Figure 3: Diabetic and Non-Diabetic Wound Healing (Source: [12])

Methodology

Study Design: This retrospective cohort study compares diabetic and non-diabetic surgical wound healing rates. Retrospective studies evaluate medical records and patient outcomes over a time to acquire valuable insights on clinical processes and outcomes.

Sample Size and Duration: The study included 100 individuals, 50 of whom had diabetes and 50 without. The patients had various surgeries from July 2023 to May 2024. With this period, we can assess wound healing following surgery.

Inclusion criteria

- Patients aged 18 years and older.
- Patients with a documented diagnosis of diabetes mellitus (diabetic group).

- Patients without a history of diabetes mellitus (non-diabetic group).
- Patients who underwent surgical procedures during the study period.

Exclusion criteria

- Patients with incomplete medical records or missing data on wound healing outcomes.
- Patients with conditions or medications known to affect wound healing (e.g., immunosuppressive therapy, chronic inflammatory diseases).
- Patients with wounds that were primarily managed non-surgically (e.g., conservative management, non-invasive treatments).

Patient Selection and Sample Size Calculation:

Patients were selected by scanning the territory care hospital's EHR database for surgical cases that met inclusion criteria.

Based on prior research comparing diabetic and non-diabetic wound healing results, the sample size was calculated using 80% power and 0.05 significance. To find clinically significant differences in wound healing rates and complications between the two groups, 100 patients were sampled, 50 from each group.

Data Collection: During data collection from EHRs, demographic and clinical factors including age, gender, clinical variables like diabetes status and surgical operation type, and wound healing outcomes like wound closure time, infection rate, and need for additional therapies were collected. All data anonymization and storage followed institutional patient confidentiality guidelines.

Statistical Analysis: The study population's demographics and clinical aspects will be described using descriptive statistics. The factors being compared will determine the statistical tests used to compare diabetes and non-diabetic groups. We will utilise $P < 0.05$ to determine statistical significance.

Ethical Considerations: The Declaration of Helsinki establishes ethical research guidelines. The Territory Care Hospital Institutional Review Board (IRB) approved the study to ensure patient confidentiality, voluntary participation, and informed consent.

Results

Description of Study Population Characteristics

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Study Population

Characteristic	Diabetic Group (n=50)	Non-Diabetic Group (n=50)
Age (years), mean $\pm$ SD	60 $\pm$ 8	58 $\pm$ 7
Gender (Male/Female)	30/20	32/18
Type of Surgery		
Orthopedic	20	22
General Surgery	15	14
Others	15	14

The study found substantial differences in surgical wound healing between diabetic and non-diabetic patients. Diabetic patients had an average age of 60 years $\pm$ 8, slightly older than non-diabetic patients (58 years $\pm$ 7).

A somewhat higher percentage of men (60% male) were in the diabetes group than in the non-diabetic group (64% male). Orthopaedic procedures made up 40% of all surgeries, while general surgery and other procedures made up 44% of non-diabetics. Both groups performed these procedures 30% of the time. These findings reveal that the diabetes and non-diabetic groups had similar surgical

treatment trends. Both groups' wound healing outcomes differed significantly. Due to slower wound healing, diabetic patients had a longer average wound closure time (28 days $\pm$ 5) compared to non-diabetic patients (21 days $\pm$ 3). Diabetes patients also experienced increased wound infections (30% vs. 12%) and needed more interventions (40% vs 18%) following surgery. These data suggest that diabetes individuals need tailored surgical wound care to improve outcomes and reduce complications.

Comparative Analysis of Wound Healing Outcomes

Table 2: Comparative Analysis of Wound Healing Outcomes

Outcome Measure	Diabetic Group (%)	Non-Diabetic Group (%)	p-value
Wound Closure Time (days), mean $\pm$ SD	28 $\pm$ 5	21 $\pm$ 3	<0.001
Incidence of Wound Infections (%)	30	12	0.023
Need for Additional Interventions (%)	40	18	0.011

This retrospective cohort study found that diabetics and non-diabetics heal wounds differently. Compared to non-diabetics (21 days), diabetics had considerably prolonged wound closure duration (28 days) ($p < 0.001$). Diabetes delays wound closure due to reduced collagen synthesis and inadequate vascular perfusion. Wound infections were 12% in non-diabetics and 30% in diabetics ($p = 0.023$). This increased susceptibility to infections highlights diabetes' immunological failure and inflammatory response, which impede wound healing and require further medical treatment. People with diabetes were more likely to need

debridement or extended antibiotic therapy than those without diabetes (40% vs. 18%, $p = 0.011$). These findings demonstrate the challenges of diabetic post-operative wound treatment and the need for holistic approaches to improve wound care and prevent complications. Understanding diabetic wound healing dynamics is essential for improving surgical results and creating appropriate treatments.

Statistical Methods Used for Analysis: Age and wound closure time were descriptively analysed using means and SD. Frequencies and percentages summarised categorical data like surgical operation and gender.

We compared diabetes and non-diabetic groups using chi-square tests for categorical variables and independent samples t-tests for continuous variables. Statistical significance was determined at $p < 0.05$.

Discussion

This retrospective cohort study found that diabetes mellitus severely impacts surgical wound healing. Diabetic patients had longer wound closure times than non-diabetics, highlighting the delays in tissue repair caused by diabetes.

Diabetics are more likely to get wound infections, which increases their post-operative risk. Diabetes patients need more treatments because treating severe wounds requires comprehensive strategy to avoid risks and maximise results.

These data show that diabetic surgical patients need particular wound care procedures and close monitoring following surgery.

Comparison Table

Table 3: Comparison Table comparing existing studies

Study Title	Study Type	Sample Size	Findings	Limitations
Current Study	Retrospective	100	Diabetic patients had prolonged wound closure times (28 ± 5 days) compared to non-diabetic (21 ± 3 days). Higher incidence of wound infections (30% vs. 12%). Increased need for additional interventions (40% vs. 18%).	Small sample size (100 patients). Retrospective design, subject to data completeness and selection biases. Single-center study, limiting generalizability.
Study 1 [13]	Prospective	250	Diabetic patients had delayed wound healing compared to non-diabetic ($p < 0.05$). Higher rates of wound complications in diabetic group.	Limited follow-up duration (<1 year). Varied surgical procedures and wound types. Single-center study, potential institutional bias.
Study 2 [14]	Meta-Analysis	300	Consistently longer wound closure times and higher infection rates in diabetic patients across multiple studies. Association between glycemic control and wound healing outcomes.	Heterogeneity across included studies (methodologies, patient populations). Potential publication bias. Limited to published literature, excluding unpublished data.
Study 3 [15]	Retrospective	150	Similar findings of prolonged wound healing and increased complications in diabetic patients. Emphasized the impact of comorbidities on outcomes.	Limited generalizability due to single-center study. Variable documentation quality in medical records. Insufficient data on long-term outcomes.

This retrospective study reveals that diabetics have significant wound healing challenges after surgery. Our study reveals that diabetic patients had prolonged wound closure times (28 ± 5 days) compared to non-diabetics (21 ± 3 days), highlighting the clinical influence of diabetes on tissue regeneration.

Diabetes patients had more wound infections (30% vs. 12%) and need more interventions (40% vs. 18%), making wound management more complicated.

Diabetics have a weakened immune system, reduced tissue perfusion, and altered collagen metabolism. Together, these variables impede wound healing and increase infection risk. Study 1, prospective 250-patient research, supports our findings of slower wound healing and greater complications among diabetics. Due to its single-

center focus and vast range of surgical procedures, the study's generalizability and bias are questioned.

Study 2's meta-analysis confirms that diabetes patients have longer wound closure timeframes and higher infection rates across studies, supporting the link between glycemic management and wound healing.

Similar to our study, Study 3 accentuates comorbidities by showing that diabetics have more problems and slower wound healing. However, the study's documentation quality and single-center design make long-term conclusions challenging.

Limitations of the Study: The retrospective technique is vulnerable to limited or erroneous medical record data collecting. Differences in surgical specialty, healthcare facility, and patient-specific clinical procedures and treatment regimens may complicate study outcomes. While 100 patients are

enough to detect substantial changes, it may limit the findings' application to wider patient populations. Future studies with larger sample sizes and prospective techniques are needed to confirm these findings and investigate other factors affecting diabetes wound healing.

Future Research Directions: Future research should address the study's weaknesses to better understand and control diabetes wound healing following surgery. Prospective research should use standardised wound examination and longitudinal follow-up to better understand diabetic wound healing. Studying growth factors, bioengineered skin replacements, and customised therapy algorithms may provide new ways to expedite wound closure and reduce problems in diabetics. Investigating how lifestyle changes like glycemic control and nutritional therapy affect wound healing could guide holistic diabetes surgical management. Since this study shows significant wound healing differences between diabetics and non-diabetics, more research is needed to improve therapeutic techniques and clinical outcomes in this vulnerable group.

Conclusion

This study illuminates diabetic surgery patients' wound healing challenges. The results show that diabetes and non-diabetics had different wound healing times, infection rates, and need for further therapies. Diabetics had 28-day wound closures and non-diabetics 21-day ones.

Diabetes-related factors include decreased tissue blood flow, collagen metabolism alterations, and diminished immune response impedes recovery. Diabetics also had greater wound infections (30% vs. 12%). Due to the increased risk of infection, diabetic surgery patients must regularly monitor wounds and devise customised treatment programmes. Debridement and prolonged antibiotic treatment are more common in diabetic wound care, which strains healthcare resources.

This study emphasises preoperative screening, accurate intraoperative management, and careful postoperative surveillance for diabetic surgical patients. Evidence-based wound care practices lower diabetic wound complications' risks, healing outcomes, and healthcare costs.

These protocols should use advanced therapy methodologies and multidisciplinary approaches. This study emphasises the need for diabetic wound care research and innovation to bridge knowledge gaps and improve clinical decision-making. This study illuminates the complex wound healing process in diabetics, which can improve clinical practice standards and surgical outcomes.

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